

Research Article

The process of producing Paedrew Giant seabass with the participation of farmers to register for geographical indication

Sataporn Deeying¹ and Tossapone Raumchimplee²

Department of Agricultural Technology, Faculty of Science and Technology, Rajabhat Rajanagarindra University, Chachoengsao, Thailand

Article Info

Received: 10 July 2024

Accepted: 22 August 2024

Online: 30 August 2024

Keywords

Process of producing Giant seabass

Paedrew Giant seabass

Register for geographical indication

Abstract

The research aims to study and compile the production process of Paedrew Giant Sea Bass with local farmers and analyze this process in preparation for Geographical Indication (GI) registration. The study focused on 29 groups of giant sea bass farmers in Bang Kluea Sub-district, Bang Pakong District, Chachoengsao Province. A participatory approach was employed to understand the production process, including ecological concepts and practical techniques for cultivating giant sea bass. Data were collected directly from the production areas, and the information was presented using visual flow diagrams, accompanied by detailed descriptions. The findings highlight that the giant sea bass farming group in Bang Kluea is characterized by advanced aquaculture techniques, expert farm management, superior fish breeds, and high-quality water. These factors enable year-round farming of giant sea bass, which typically reach 5-8 kilograms after 18-20 months, due to the unique salinity conditions of the Bang Pakong River. In contrast, other areas can only raise smaller white snapper (700-900 grams) within 4-5 months. The Chachoengsao group practices a comprehensive farming process, from breeding to growing fish to giant size, ensuring high survival and growth rates. The fish produced are known for their large size, firm and chewy texture, high nutritional value (rich in omega 3 and 6), and absence of fishy odor, thanks to a specialized bleeding technique called "Ike-jime," adapted from Japanese practices. This technique maintains the freshness and quality of the fish, resulting in white, clear flesh with a good texture. Additionally, the fish exhibit a rainbow-colored sheen due to a curing process that integrates fat into the flesh. The entire production process is divided into three main stages: the production of white snapper fry, raising the fish to market size, and growing them into giant sea bass. Throughout each stage, there is a strong emphasis on maintaining high standards of quality, which is crucial for meeting the criteria required for GI registration. This comprehensive approach not only enhances the product's market value but also positions Paedrew Giant Sea Bass as a unique and high-quality product suitable for both local and international markets.

2754-7825 / © 2024 The Authors.
Published by Young Wise Pub. Ltd
This is an open access article under
CC BY license.

To cite this article

Deeying, S., and Raumchimplee, T. (2024). The process of producing Paedrew Giant seabass with the participation of farmers to register for geographical indication. *Journal for the Agriculture, Biotechnology and Education*, 4(2), 25-35. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13689632>

Introduction

Giant seabass has key breeding areas in the provinces of Chachoengsao, Surat Thani, Nakhon Si Thammarat, Pattani, and Songkhla, which together account for 62.10% of the total farming area, 56.44% of the total number of farms, and 77.03% of the total aquaculture production (Department of Fisheries Policy and Strategic Development, Department

¹ Assistant Professor, Rajabhat Rajanagarindra University, Chachoengsao province, 24000, Thailand. E-mail: sataporn.deeying@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0005-8216-4918

² Lecturer, Rajabhat Rajanagarindra University, Chachoengsao province, 24000, Thailand. E-mail: tossapone1971@gmail.com ORCID: 0009-0001-7687-827X

of Fisheries). Giant seabass is an economically significant fish that can be bred and raised in earthen ponds in both brackish and saltwater environments. Nearly 100% of the seabass sold in the market are farmed, with a typical market size known as “plate-size seabass” weighing approximately 700-900 grams. However, the giant seabass of Chachoengsao Province, known for its larger size of 5-8 kilograms, is particularly distinctive. This variety has firm, thick flesh, a delicious flavor, a fresh scent, high Omega content, and is free from any fishy odor. The product is available year-round, which sets it apart from seabass in other provinces.

Additionally, giant seabass in Chachoengsao Province is exclusively bred and raised locally from juvenile to adult stages. This uniqueness has driven the farmers to seek Geographical Indication (GI) registration for giant seabass as a provincial specialty product. GI registration would standardize the product, build consumer confidence, and highlight its unique characteristics, ultimately increasing farmers' income through the sale of a distinctive and standardized product in global markets.

The GI registration process requires comprehensive preparation, including geographical and biological information, production factors, and management processes. Farmers and stakeholders must be involved in every step to emphasize the importance of participation in preparing for GI registration. For giant seabass farming, this includes planning, pond preparation, broodstock selection, fry release, feeding, sorting, and harvesting. It is essential to support and validate these practices with scientific data to confirm the unique identity of Paet Rio giant seabass and prepare for its GI registration

Objectives

- To study and compile the context of the Paet Rio giant seabass production process in collaboration with farmers.
- To analyze the Paet Rio giant seabass production process in preparation for Geographical Indication (GI) registration.

Research Framework

The study of the participatory management process for the production of Paet Rio giant seabass by farmers will be conducted under the theories and concepts related to giant seabass production. This will be linked with the preparation of information for GI registration in Thailand, with an emphasis on participation. The study will collect comprehensive data related to 1) seabass fry production, 2) raising seabass to market size, and 3) raising seabass to full-grown giant size, with the aim of identifying the unique geographical indications of Paet Rio giant seabass. The conceptual framework is summarized as follows:

Giant sea bass farming is a unique area with distinctive farming characteristics, this led to farmers' demand to upgrade the giant seabass to become a provincial product by requesting registration as a Geographic Indication (GI) product to become a standard product, build confidence among consumers who are interested in products with special features, it is unique, which will lead to increased income for farmers from selling unique products and standard products that will lead to trade in the world market, which the application for GI registration must have a process for preparing all-around information, both geographic information and biological information of the area, production factors, production management processes to obtain comprehensive and important information in preparing for GI registration.

Figure 1. The participatory management process of PaedRiew Giant Sea Bass

Research Methodology

Population and Sample Group

The population consists of giant seabass farmers in Bang Pakong District, Chachoengsao Province.

The sample group includes a network of 29 large-scale giant seabass farmers in Bang Kluai Subdistrict, Bang Pakong District, Chachoengsao Province.

Research Instruments

The research instruments for this study include participatory spatial analysis of the giant seabass production process and the application of the Ecosystem Approach to Aquaculture (EAA) for giant seabass farming. Data collection tools include direct observation of production areas, photography of the production process, and the presentation of the data in the form of process flow diagrams, which serve as the primary medium for presenting the findings, along with descriptive explanations of each diagram.

Research Procedure

The participatory production management process for giant seabass farming in Paet Rio, aiming for Geographical Indication (GI) registration, involves the following steps:

- Step 1. Preparation before studying the giant seabass production process.
- Step 2. Data collection in the production areas of giant seabass.
- Step 3. Data compilation, analysis, and presentation.
- Step 4. Presentation and feedback of the giant seabass production process data.

Figure 2. Research plan for the participatory production process of PaedRiew Giant Sea Bass by farmers aimed at Geographical Indication registration.

Figure 3. Research implementation steps

Research Findings

The giant seabass producer group in Bang Kluai Subdistrict, Bang Pakong District, Chachoengsao Province, is a large-scale enterprise consisting of 29 members. The group's strength lies in their advanced cultivation techniques, where the seabass farmers possess significant expertise, effective farm management, superior fish breeds, excellent water quality, and in-depth knowledge of rearing giant seabass. These key strengths provide them a competitive advantage over other regions that cannot sustain seabass farming year-round. The natural conditions in Chachoengsao Province, particularly the salinity of the Bang Pakong River, allow for seabass farming throughout the year. The farming process for giant seabass takes approximately 18-20 months, with the fish reaching a weight of over 5 kilograms, whereas in other regions, seabass farming typically produces smaller fish (700-900 grams) within 4-5 months.

The Bang Kluai group manages the entire seabass production cycle, from breeding to rearing the fish to their full size. The primary seabass breeding centers are located in Song Khlong Subdistrict and Tha Sa-an Subdistrict, both in Bang Pakong District, which are the largest seabass breeding areas in the region. The group includes breeders, hatchery operators, and those responsible for nurturing seabass from fry to full-sized fish. The resulting giant seabass exhibit several distinctive characteristics: 1) The fish are large, robust, with firm, white, and beautiful flesh that does not disintegrate during cooking and lacks a fishy odor. 2) They are highly nutritious, rich in Omega 3 and Omega 6, and contain brain-healthy nutrients directly sourced from natural water. 3) The fish have a delicious flavor, are fresh, clean, and free from chemicals, as no chemicals or antibiotics are used in the farming process. 4) The fish lack the typical fishy smell due to a blood-draining process, preserving the flesh's freshness and quality. 5) The filleted fish display a rainbow sheen (achieved by fat integration into the flesh, known as "aging"), resulting in tender, translucent flesh. 6) The scales are shiny and glossy, with the skin remaining white after descaling. The fish are long, with thick backs and firm flesh. The group has adopted the Japanese technique of "Ikejime" for bleeding the fish, which eliminates the fishy odor, preserves the flesh, and maintains a good texture. Additionally, the group employs unique processing techniques that enhance the flavor, sweetness, and texture of the flesh, resulting in a product with a distinctive rainbow sheen.

The production process of giant seabass in this region is divided into three main stages: 1) seabass fry production, 2) rearing the fish to a marketable size, and 3) raising the fish to their full giant size. Each stage is critical, starting with the preparation of broodstock, hatching, and nurturing the fry to produce high-quality seabass with good growth rates, high survival rates, and the appropriate size for farmers' needs. The process involves careful pond preparation, fry release, feed management, water quality control, harvesting of market-sized fish, and raising the fish to their full size as giant seabass. This comprehensive production cycle, from breeding to processing, ensures that the seabass produced meets high-quality standards, adding value to the product and enhancing the farmers' competitiveness in the market.

Figure 1. Summary of the Production Process of Giant White Sea Bass

Figure 2. Summary of the White Snapper Fry Production Process

Figure 3. Summary of the White Sea Bass (Size) Production Process

Figure 4. Summary of the Giant Sea Bass Production Process

Discussion and Conclusion

The key strengths of the giant seabass production by the producer group are rooted in the cultivation techniques. The seabass farmers possess significant expertise, effective farm management, superior fish breeds, excellent water quality, and substantial knowledge in rearing giant seabass. As a result, they produce giant seabass with the following characteristics: 1) The fish are large, robust, and strong with firm, white, beautiful flesh that does not disintegrate when cooked. The flesh is firm yet tender, does not break apart during cooking, and is free from any fishy odor. 2) The fish are highly nutritious, rich in Omega 3 and Omega 6, and contain nutrients beneficial for brain health due to the fish obtaining minerals directly from natural water sources. 3) The fish have a delicious flavor, are fresh, clean, and free from chemicals (as no chemicals or antibiotics are used in the farming process). 4) The flesh lacks any fishy smell due to the blood being effectively drained from the fish, maintaining freshness, white color, and preventing rapid deterioration. 5) The filleted fish exhibit a rainbow sheen (achieved by fat integration with the flesh, known as "aging"), resulting in tender, translucent flesh (weighing 1 kilogram). 6) The scales are shiny and glossy, with the skin remaining white after descaling (white and beautiful skin). The fish are long with thick backs (long and thick), and the flesh is firm (farmers believe this is due to the soil properties in the seabass farming area). Additionally, the producer group has adopted the technique of bleeding the fish, which effectively removes any fishy odor. The process, performed by skilled personnel using a method called "Ikejime" derived from Japanese practices for preparing fish for raw consumption, involves bleeding the fish through the gills. This technique eliminates any fishy odor, preserves the flesh for an extended period, and ensures the flesh remains white and translucent with a good texture. The processing of the fish is carried out using unique techniques by the farmers, resulting in flesh that is flavorful, sweeter, firmer, and exhibits a rainbow sheen (due to fat integration with the flesh, known as "aging"), a distinct characteristic of the giant seabass produced by the group. The production process of giant seabass has been divided by the researcher into three stages: 1) the production process of seabass fry, 2) the process of growing seabass to a marketable size, and 3) the process of rearing seabass to become giant seabass. Each stage of the production process is critical, starting from the crucial steps of breeding and nurturing seabass fry, including the preparation of broodstock and the provision of food during the first 2-3 weeks after hatching. The majority of seabass used for breeding come from sources maintained by the Department of Fisheries. According to the Department of Fisheries (2001), the nurturing of seabass fry is divided into two phases: the first phase involves raising the fry from hatching until they are one month old, which is crucial for their survival. Subsequently, the fry are raised in cages until they reach a size of 3 centimeters or more, at which point they are ready for sale. The seabass fry farms are considered the primary production system in the large-scale giant seabass production chain, providing fry to members who require them, enhancing the efficiency of seabass farming. This system begins with nurturing the fry until they are ready for further farming, allowing members to farm throughout the year, reducing the time and improving the quality of farming for seabass farmers. The fish grow faster and are ready for sale more quickly. Since seabass have different eating behaviors from other fish, preferring fresh food and not eating leftovers, producers must understand this behavior to feed seabass correctly, which directly affects their growth. The Sriracha Fisheries Research Station (2003) noted that while feeding fish might seem simple, it actually requires an understanding of the principles, methods, and environmental changes in which the fish live, as well as the fish's habits and behaviors. These factors must be integrated to ensure that the fish eat well, make the most of their food, and minimize waste, as aquatic feed is a crucial factor in aquaculture production. The distinctive characteristics of giant seabass farming, unique to the area and reflective of the local identity, have led to a demand among farmers to elevate giant seabass as a provincial specialty product by registering it as a Geographical Indication (GI) product. This would establish it as a standard product, build consumer confidence in a product with unique characteristics, and increase farmers' income through the sale of standardized, unique products in global markets. The GI registration process requires thorough preparation of geographic and biological information, production factors, and management processes, with active participation from farmers and producers in every step to highlight the importance of collective involvement in the GI registration process.

References

- Ambasankar K, Ahamad AS, Syamadaya J. *Nutritional requirements of Asian seabass, Lates calcarifer*. National training on cage culture of seabass; 2009 Dec 14-23; Kochi, India: Central marine fisheries research institute; 2009.
- Amornsakul T. *The feeding frequency and feeding ration of sea bass, Lates calcarifer Bloch culture in earth pond*. Technical report. Songkhla, Thailand: Prince of Songkhla University; 1996.
- Asia. Aquaculture. 1997;151: 283-313.
- Biswas G, Thirunavukkarasu AR, Sundaray JK, Kailasam M. *Optimization of feeding frequency of Asian sea bass (Lates calcarifer) fry reared in net cages under brackishwater environment*. Aquaculture. 2010;305: 26-31.
- Boonyaratpalin M, Wanakowat J. *Effect of thiamine, riboflavin, pantothenic acid and inositol on growth, feed efficiency and mortality of juvenile seabass*. In: Kaushik SJ, Luget P, editors. Fish nutrition in practice. Biarritz, France; 1993. p. 819-828.
- Boonyaratpalin M. Asian seabass, *Lates calcarifer*. In: Wilson RP, editor. Handbook of nutrient requirements of finfish. Florida, USA: CRC Press; 1991. p. 5-11.
- Boonyaratpalin M. *Nutrient requirements of marine food fish cultured in Southeast*
- Catacutan MR, Coloso RM. *Effect of dietary protein to energy ratios on growth, survival, and body composition of juvenile Asian seabass, Lates calcarifer*. Aquaculture. 1995;131: 125-133.
- Catacutan MR, Coloso RM. *Growth of juvenile Asian seabass, Lates calcarifer, fed varying carbohydrate and lipid levels*. Aquaculture. 1997;149: 137-144.
- Coloso RM, Murillo DP, Borlongan IG, Catacutan MR. *Requirement of juvenile*
- Department of Fisheries, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives. (2020). Report on brackish water fish production statistics for the year 2017-2018. Fisheries Statistics Group, Fisheries Policy and Development Plan Division.
- Department of Fisheries. (2001). Brackish water fish farming. Bangkok: The Agricultural Cooperatives Printing Press of Thailand Co., Ltd.
- Department of Fisheries. (2020). Brackish water fish farm statistics for the year 2019 (Document No. 12/2020). Fisheries Statistics Group, Fisheries Policy and Development Plan Division, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives.
- Department of Fisheries. (2020). Report on brackish water fish production statistics by year, province, and species classification. Retrieved from https://stat.fisheries.go.th/services/services_report/showreport.php (Accessed November 20, 2020).
- Department of Intellectual Property. (2016). Introduction to intellectual property. Retrieved from <http://e-learning.ipthailand.go.th> (Accessed May 15, 2020).
- Department of Intellectual Property. (2018). Introduction to intellectual property. Retrieved from <http://e-learning.ipthailand.go.th> (Accessed January 15, 2021).
- FIGIS. Global aquaculture production 1950-2004. Rome, Italy: FAO; 2006. Information technology center. Fisheries statistics of Thailand 2010. Bangkok, Thailand: Department of Fisheries; 2012. 96 p. Report No.:12/2012. Thai.
- Fisheries Club, Faculty of Fisheries. (1988). Seabass farming (Principles and practices). Bangkok: Chonnontree Publishing.
- Gatlin DM. Principles of fish nutrition. Mississippi, USA: Southern Regional Aquaculture Center; 2010 Jul. 8 p. Publication No.:5003.
- Glencross B, Rutherford N. *A determination of the quantitative requirements for docosahexaenoic acid for juvenile barramundi (Lates calcarifer)*. Aquac Nutr. 2011 Apr;17(2): 536-548. Epub 2010 Sep 14.
- Glencross B. *The nutritional management of barramundi, Lates calcarifer-a review*. Aquac Nutr. 2006;12(4): 291-309.
- Harpaz S, Hakim Y, Barki A, Karplus I, Slosman T, Eroldogan OT. *Effects of different feeding levels during day and/or night on growth and brush-border enzyme activity in juvenile Lates calcarifer reared in freshwater re-circulating tanks*. Aquaculture. 2005;248: 325-335.
- Hemtanon P, Keanduang C, Hemtanon I. *Survival and growth rate of seabass (Lates calcarifer) using brine shrimp adult enriched with Spirulina platensis*. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Nakornsrihammarat coastal fisheries research and development center; 2004. 9 p. Technical report No.:17/2004. Thai.
- Jeungyampin S, Juntanachooklin C, Sirikul B, Wattanakul V, Tejnawong S, Kojasingha S. Experiment on feeding frequency of seabass (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch) at the size of inches. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National
- Keanduang C, Hemtanon P, Mala A. *Experiment on using water flea (Moina macrocopa) to replace brine shrimp (Artemia sp.) for nursing seabass (Lates calcarifer)*. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Nakornsrihammarat coastal fisheries research and development center; 2000. Technical report. Thai.
- Lekhanukit, A. (2009). Growth study of seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) fed with different feeds. Special Problem. Bachelor of Science in Fisheries (Aquaculture) Curriculum, Maejo University-Chumphon, Maejo University.
- Maneewong S, Ruengpanich N, Tatthanon T, Kraisinghadeja P. Experiment on feeding seabass larvae (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch) age 3-12 days with different kind of food. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 2004. 13 p. Technical report No.:3/2004. Thai.
- Maneewong, S., & Phongsuwan, P. (2015). Seabass farming in nylon cages. *Annual Report 1971-1972*. Songkhla: Department of Fisheries, Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Bureau, Coastal Aquaculture Research Institute.

- Millamena OM. Review of SEAFDEC/AQD fish nutrition and feed development research. In: Santiago CB, Coloso RM, Millamena OM, Borlongan IG, editors. Feeds for small-scale aquaculture. Proceedings of the national seminar- workshop on fish nutrition and feeds; 1994 Jun 1-2; Iloilo, Philippines: SEAFDEC Aquaculture Department; 1994. p. 52-63.
- Office of Agricultural Economics Research. (2014). Economic production and marketing of seabass in cages. *Agricultural Economics Research Document No. 106*. Office of Agricultural Economics, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives.
- Panichsook P. Possibility of using rotifer (*Brachionus plicatilis*) and water flea (*Moina macrocopa*) for nursing of seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) of using the nauplii of brine shrimp (*Artemia* sp.). Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 1996. 11 p. Technical report No.:12/1996. Thai.
- Peet C. Farmed barramundi *Lates calcarifer*. Seafood watch and the seafood report. Australia: Monterey Bay Aquarium; 2006.
- Petchmanee T, Assavaaree M. Effect of using rotifer (*Brachionus plicatilis*) fed with different feeds for nursing seabass larvae (*Lates calcarifer*). Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 1991. 11p. Technical report No.:3/1991. Thai.
- Petchmanee T, Maneewong S, Akkayanont P. Feeding levels of early stage seabass larvae, *Lates calcarifer* (Bloch) on rotifer *Brachionus plicatilis*. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 2004. 19 p. Technical report. Thai.
- Petchmanee T, Pongmaneerat J, Iizawa M. The relationship between the density of rotifer, *Brachionus plicatilis* and the amount of rotifer ingested by 4-14 day seabass larvae. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 1984. 8 p. Technical report. Thai.
- Petchmanee T, Rojanapittayakul S, Gate A. Technique of using rotifer (*Brachionus rotundiformis*) and brackish cladoceran (*Diaphanosoma* sp.) to replace newly hatched brine shrimp (*Artemia* sp.) for nursing seabass (*Lates calcarifer*). Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 1999. 10 p. Technical report No.:9/1999. Thai.
- Phak Phanang River Basin Development Project under the Royal Initiative. (2012). Seabass farming. Retrieved from <http://www.fisheries.go.th/images/aqua/Lates%20calcarifer.jpg> (Accessed November 20, 2020).
- Phuket Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Center. (2020). Seabass (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch) farming in large cages. Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Bureau, Department of Fisheries, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives.
- Pimoljinda T, Boonyaratpalin M. Study on vitamin B1 requirement of seabass *Lates calcarifer* Bloch. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Phuket brackishwater fisheries station; 1990. 15 p. Technical report No.: 6/1990. Thai.
- Plaipech, P. (2014). The progress of seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) fish feed research. *KKU Research Journal*, 19(4), 571-584.
- Prasertsom, S. (2004). Acute toxicity of ammonia on seabass fry *Lates calcarifer* (Bloch). *Technical Document No. 10/2004*. Songkhla: Department of Fisheries, Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Bureau, Coastal Aquaculture Research Institute.
- Rayong Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Center. (2015). Seabass farming. Retrieved from <http://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=www.fisheries.go.th/cfrayong/index.php> (Accessed November 20, 2020).
- Rimmer MA, Reed A. Effects of nutritional enhancement of live food organisms on growth and survival of Barramundi/Seabass *Lates calcarifer* (Bloch) larvae. *Adv Trop Aquac*. 1989;9: 611-623.
- Rojanapittayakul, S., Kongkamnoed, J., & Chaimongkol, A. (2004). Seabass (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch) farming with low protein feed interchanged with normal protein feed: Effects on growth and feed utilization efficiency. *Technical Document No. 9/2004*. Songkhla: Department of Fisheries, Coastal Fisheries Research and Development Bureau, Coastal Aquaculture Research Institute.
- Rojanapittayakul S, Kongkumnerd J, Petchmanee T. Cost reduction of 15-28 days old sea bass (*Lates calcarifer*) larval rearing fed with ongrown *Artemia*. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 2000. 12 p. Technical report No.:6/2000. Thai.
- Sakares W, Boonyaratpalin M, Unprasert N, Kumpang P. Optimum dietary protein energy ratio in seabass feed I. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Rayong brackishwater fisheries station; 1988. 20 p. Technical report No.:7/1988. Thai.
- Sakares W, Boonyaratpalin M, Unprasert N, Kumpang P. Optimum dietary protein energy ratio in seabass feed II. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Rayong brackishwater fisheries station; 1989. 22 p. Technical report No.:8/1989. Thai.
- Sakares W, Kumpang P. Effects of feeding frequency on growth performance and production of seabass *Lates calcarifer* (Bloch) cultured in net cage. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Rayong brackishwater fisheries station; 1989. 21 p. Technical report No.:2/1989. Thai.
- Sakharet, W., & Sukbunthong, S. (1982). Experimental seabass farming in cages with different stocking densities. *Annual Report 1982*. Rayong Fisheries Station, Brackish Water Fisheries Division.
- Salama AJ, Al-Harbi MA. Response of the Asian sea bass *Lates calcarifer* fingerlings to different feeding rates and feeding frequencies reared in hypersaline condition. *JKAU: Mar Sci*. 2007;18:63-81.
- Salama AJ. Effects of different feeding frequency on the growth, survival and feed conversion ratio of the Asian sea bass *Lates calcarifer* juveniles reared under hypersaline seawater of the Red Sea. *Aquac Res*. 2008;39(6): 561-567.
- seabass Lates calcarifer Bloch for tryptophan*. The VI international symposium on fish nutrition and feeding; 1993 Oct 4-7; Hobart, Australia; 1993.
- Sermwatanakul, A., et al. (2005). Aquatic feed and feed production. Bangkok: Agricultural Cooperatives Printing Press.

- Sriracha Fisheries Research Station, Academic Support Division, Faculty of Fisheries. (2003). Seabass farming. Retrieved from http://www.ku.ac.th/emagazinejuly46/agri/fish_kapong.html (Accessed November 20, 2020).
- Srirayaporn T. Suitable protein and lipid levels in dry pellet for juvenile white sea bass, *Lates calcarifer* [Msc thesis]. Bangkok, Thailand: Chulalongkorn University; 1996. Thai.
- Tanasomwang V, Rittitum S, Thongrod S. Production and nutrition of rotifers (*Brachionus plicatilis*) fed *Chlorella* sp. and supplemented feeds. Thai
- Tantikitti C, Onkong S, Srisook S, Mahankich S. Effects of feeding level and feeding frequency on growth, feed efficiency and nitrogen and phosphorus loss in seabass (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch) fed diets with defatted soybean meal partially replacing fishmeal. Songklanakarin J Sci Technol. 2007;29(3):725-736. Fisheries Gazette 2006;59(4): 310-322.
- Thongrod S, Suthemeechaikul N. Experiment on feeding rate of rotifer by seabass larvae. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Satun brackishwater fisheries station; 1983. 22 p. Technical report No.:8/1983. Thai.
- Thongrod S, Tamtin M, Plaietch P, Kuekaew J, Chaikul SL. Feeding trial on seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) larviculture using zooplankton harvested from shrimp pond. Proceedings of annual seminar on fisheries; 2006 Jun 25-27; Bangkok, Thailand; 2006. p. 269-280. Thai.
- Tu WC, Muhlhusler BS, James MJ, Stone DAJ, Gibson RA. Dietary alpha-linolenic Acid does not enhance accumulation of omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids in barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*). Comp Biochem Physiol-B. 2013;164: 29-37.
- Tucker JW, Russell DJ, Rimmer MA. Barramundi culture: A success story for aquaculture in Asia and Australia. World Aquaculture. 2002;33: 53-59.
- Turchini GM, Torstensen BE, Ng WK. Fish oil replacement in finfish nutrition. Rev Aquaculture. 2009;1: 10-57.
- Vartak VR, Kumar S. Effects of live food organisms and formulated diets on growth survival, and body protein of Asian sea bass fry (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch). Isr J Aquacult-Bamid. 2009;61(1): 63-67.
- Walton MJ. Aspect of amino acid metabolism in teleost fish. In: Cowey CB, Mackie AM, Bell JG, editors. Nutrition and feeding in fish. London, England: Academic Press; 1985. p. 47-67.
- Wanakawat J, Boonyaratpalin M, Donyadont Y, Assavaaree M, Pakirana S. The optimal level vitamin B6 in seabass, *Lates calcarifer* diet. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 1989. Technical report. Thai.
- Wattanukul V, Jeungyampin S, Sirikul B, Tejnarawong S, Juntanachooklin C. Effects of feeding frequency on the growth of sea bass *Lates calcarifer* (Bloch), cultured for marketable size in floating net cages. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: National institute of coastal aquaculture; 1985. 21 p. Technical report No.:30/1985. Thai. institute of coastal aquaculture; 1985. 19 p. Technical report No.:15/1985. Thai.
- Williams KC, Barlow CG, Rodgers L, Hockings I, Agcopra C, Ruscoe I. Asian seabass *Lates calcarifer* perform well when fed pellet diets high in protein and lipid. Aquaculture. 2003;225: 191-206.
- Williams KC, Barlow CG. Dietary requirement and optimal feeding practices for barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*). Research report. Canberra, Australia: Fisheries R&D Corporation; 1999.
- Williams KC, Rimmer MA. The future of feeds and feeding of marine finfish in the Asia-Pacific region: the need to develop alternative aquaculture feed. The regional workshop on low value/"trash fish" in the Asia-Pacific region; 2005 Jun 7-9; Hanoi, Vietnam; 2005.
- Wongsamnung, S., & Maneewong, S. (1974). Artificial breeding of seabass (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch). *Annual Scientific Report 1973-1974*, 62-83. Songkhla Fisheries Station, Department of Fisheries.
- Wongsomnuek S, Maneewong S. Experiment on artificial breeding and larval rearing of the sea bass (*Lates calcarifer* Bloch). Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Songkhla marine fisheries station; 1973. 22 p. Technical report No.:5/1973. Thai.
- Worajin A, Homchong T, Tansutapanich A. Rearing of white seabass *Lates calcarifer* (Bloch), fingerling with three strains of Artemia. Chonburi, Thailand: Srinakharinwirot University, Bangsaen campus; 1986. 9 p. Technical report. Thai.
- Youngvanitset K, Teawsee K, Junmuang P. Comparison on nursing of 15-28 days seabass larvae (*Lates calcarifer*) with 3 different feeds. Department of Fisheries, Thailand: Narathiwat coastal fisheries research and development center; 2004. 19 p. Technical report No.:39/2004. Thai.

